

Cultural Clash in Work Ethics and Communication Style: A Case Study in Japanese Based Manufacturing Company in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Cultural differences in values, norms, and language represent a significant challenge for Indonesian employees working in multinational companies. These disparities often give rise to misunderstandings and tensions between local staff and foreign expatriates. This paper seeks to explore the cultural friction specifically between Japanese and Indonesian work cultures, aiming to help organizations cultivate a more inclusive environment and minimize the risk of future conflicts. This research employs a qualitative approach, utilizing in-depth interviews with both Indonesian employees and Japanese expatriates at a Japanese based manufacturing company in Indonesia. The major findings are the differences in work ethics between Indonesian workers and Japanese expatriates lie in their perceptions of the importance of work, appreciation of time, and future orientation. In term of communication there are different style of communication between Indonesian employees, who are typically place strong emphasis on interpersonal relationships, while Japanese Expatriates focused on work-related-communication. Another prominent distinction lies in communication structure: Japanese expatriates prefer two-way, structured, and consensus-oriented communication, while Indonesian employees typically engage in casual and flexible communication styles.

KEYWORDS: Culture, Cultural Clash, Work Ethics, Intercultural Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, multinational corporations are increasingly expanding their operations beyond their home countries to remain competitive in the international marketplace. Indonesia has emerged as an appealing destination for foreign investment due to its large population, strategic geography, rich natural resources, and relatively low labor costs. These factors have drawn numerous foreign enterprises, including Japanese companies, to establish a presence in Indonesia. However, this influx of Japanese businesses and expatriates brings with it a set of cultural challenges, particularly for Indonesian employees who engage in direct interactions with them. Communication and collaboration across these distinct cultures become more intricate due to variations in values, social norms, and language.

The Japanese are widely known for their exceptional work ethic, marked by a high level of discipline and a strong sense of responsibility toward both time and duties. On the other hand, Indonesian workplace culture often emphasizes harmony, mutual understanding, and flexibility. Japanese expatriates also demonstrate a notable dedication to their customers. Their customer-centric mindset leads them to avoid directly refusing or negotiating with clients, as doing so could be perceived as failing to uphold customer satisfaction.

In terms of communication style, Japanese expatriates tend to be indirect and selective in sharing information. They also place a strong emphasis on organizational hierarchy and frequently seek comprehensive details, which results in extensive questioning. Some Indonesian staff members reported feeling pressured or uncomfortable, interpreting the tone and delivery of these questions as overly intense or critical. These feelings were further exacerbated by language barriers, which made it difficult to provide clear responses or explanations.

Since both groups are non-native English speakers, misinterpretations and mismatched expectations were common. What Japanese expatriates intended to convey often differed from what Indonesian employees understood and implemented. Accents and language limitations also meant that more time was needed to ensure mutual understanding, occasionally causing inefficiencies in daily operations. Such challenges are typical for employees navigating cross-cultural interactions in a multinational workplace.

Aligned with the objectives of this study, an exploratory approach is necessary to obtain a comprehensive understanding of individual experiences and perceptions related to cross-cultural conflicts. The study seeks to examine the cultural differences within

the company, identify the root causes behind the contrasting work ethics and communication styles, and offer practical recommendations to prevent or reduce potential conflicts stemming from these cultural differences.

Ultimately, this study aims to offer valuable insights that can assist the company in fostering a more inclusive and harmonious work environment for both Japanese and Indonesian employees. By doing so, it seeks to reduce the likelihood of misunderstandings or tensions caused by intercultural interactions. Furthermore, the findings of this research are expected to provide meaningful guidance for other multinational organizations facing similar cross-cultural challenges in the Indonesian context.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Culture

Culture is the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another [1]. Culture consists of unwritten rules of the social game, catchword for all patterns of thinking, feeling, and acting—not only activities that are meant to refine the mind but also ordinary, everyday behaviors, such as greeting, eating, showing or hiding emotions, and maintaining physical distance. Culture is not merely consisting of traditions or societal values but as being reflected in the way people communicate [2]

B. Culture Clash

Culture clash is a situation in which the diverging attitudes, moral, opinions, or customs of two dissimilar culture or subcultures are revealed [3]. Culture clash also defined as conflict arising from the interaction of people with different cultural values [15]. Cultural clash can be concluded and seen as the initial stage of interactions where differences are noticed, and culture conflict represents a further escalation where these differences become a source of friction and conflict. In the process, differences are cast as the result of so-called negative and inherent shared behavioral characteristics or tendencies rather than as a matter of divergent life experiences or differential access to resources, power, and/or status.

Culture clash often leads to misunderstandings, and stereotyping, where differences are framed as negative inherent traits rather than results of historical and structural inequalities. Individuals from non-dominant groups may experience identity threats, exclusion, and stress, affecting their well-being and sense of belonging and dissatisfaction. [4][5]

C. Hofstede's Culture Dimension

Dimensions of culture divides into six categories as 1.) Power Distance, 2.) Collectivism and Individualism, 3.) Masculinity and Femininity, 4.) Uncertainty Avoidance, 5.) Long-Term and Short-Term Orientation, and 6.) Indulgence and Restraints.[1] This study focuses specifically on two dimensions of Hofstede's cultural framework: Power Distance and Uncertainty Avoidance, in alignment with the business issues discussed in Introduction. These dimensions are selected based on the characteristics of Japanese expatriates, who highly value organizational hierarchy and structured communication flow. Moreover, the expatriates tend to exhibit a strong need for clarity, often demonstrated through asking highly detailed questions to their team members. This behavior indicates a potential for cultural clashes with local Indonesian employees, who may hold different values and working styles.

Power Distance can be defined as the extent to which the less powerful members of institutions and organizations within a country expect and accept that power is distributed unequally. This dimension is rooted in the inequality inherent in society, where some individuals are perceived as bigger, stronger, or smarter than others, earning them more status and respect.[1]

Uncertainty is not only a personal experience but can also be collectively shared within a society. These feelings of uncertainty are acquired and learned, forming part of a society's cultural heritage. They are transmitted and reinforced through fundamental institutions such as family, education, and government. To cope with uncertainty, societies have developed various mechanisms in the domains of technology, law, and religion. Technology helps mitigate uncertainties related to nature, laws and regulations provide structure to reduce unpredictability in human behavior, and religion offers comfort in the face of uncertainties that cannot be controlled, sometimes even providing the ultimate assurance of life after death or victory over adversaries.[1]

D. Hall's Intercultural Communication

Communication is a selective process heavily influenced by culture and the brevity of cultural communication can lead to misunderstandings in cross-cultural exchanges.[6] Concept of context in communication also introduced, which refers to the extent to which a culture relies on non-verbal, situational, and historical factors to understand messages.

Communication cultures classified into two main types: 1.) High Context, and 2.) Low Context. In high-context cultures, communication is implied within the situational context, social relationships, and shared understanding. Communication in these cultures tends to be indirect, implicit, and heavily reliant on non-verbal cues like body language, facial expressions, and tone of voice. In contrast, low-context cultures rely on explicit, direct, and verbal communication, with less dependence on social context. Messages are more literal and require fewer assumptions. In this type of communication, message is clear and the listener will infer meaning without further explanation, communication is straightforward to the point, and silence is often perceived as uncomfortable or as a sign of confusion.[6]

E. Lewi's Culture Categories

Culture categorized into three types: 1.) Linear Active Culture, 2.) Multi Active Culture, and 3.) Reactive Culture. In linear active culture, people in these cultures plan meticulously, follow schedules, and prefer direct communication. People focus to do one thing at time with a structured and organized approach, they believe this approach enhances efficiency and productivity. In multi active culture, people prioritize relationships over strict schedules and are less concerned with punctuality. People are highly flexible, often engaging in multiple tasks simultaneously in an unstructured manner. While in reactive culture, people rarely initiate action or discussion; instead, they prefer to listen first, understand the other party's position, and then respond carefully. They focus intently on the speaker, avoid interrupting, and consider silence a sign of respect. Reactive individuals do not reply immediately; instead, they take time to reflect before responding to ensure their words carry proper weight and deference. [7]

F. Work Ethics

Work ethic is a unique response of an individual, group, or society toward life. This response arises from internalized beliefs, which then form habits or work character within a person or community [16]. In essence, work ethic reflects an internal drive that motivates someone to behave and act according to the best values in their work, for the sake of a broader purpose. Work ethic also includes a system of values that underpins or guides a person's orientation in carrying out tasks and responsibilities.

There are seven dimensions of work ethic as follow: 1.) Centrality of Work, the belief that work itself is important as a main activity in the life of a person, 2.) Self-Reliance, representing the individual's vigor toward independence, 3.) Hard Work, the belief that a sustained level of work is the best way to achieve a feeling of accomplishment, 4.) Leisure, beliefs and attitudes regarding the relevance of non-work activities, 5.) Morality-Ethic, believing in a just and moral existence, 6.) Delay of Gratification, the capacity to delay rewards until a later date, 7.) Wasted Time, the consciousness of the value of time.[8]

G. Previous Research

Japanese firms, which are traditionally shaped by homogeneous cultural assumptions, face difficulties integrating foreign professionals due to rigid hierarchical structures and lack of role flexibility[9]. Not only about hierarchical structures and role, difficulties come from role ambiguity and conflict, though in different ways, non-Japanese employees in Japanese based company in Australia struggle with unclear job expectations and insufficient cultural orientation, while Japanese local hires face tensions arising from their dual cultural affiliation.[10] In the Indonesian context, finds that Japanese and Indonesian staff develop complex, fluid relationships shaped by personal, cultural, and organizational factors.[11] Disparities in values on Hofstede's cultural dimensions—such as power distance, collectivism versus individualism, and uncertainty avoidance—contribute to misunderstanding and workplace tension between Japanese and Indonesian employees.[12] Japanese expatriate workers and Indonesian local employees also have communication challenges in their shared work environments. Both groups face communication barriers, particularly in language use and work culture. Japanese workers challenged with informal communication and perceived unprofessionalism, while Indonesian workers struggled with rigid communication and indirect feedback from their Japanese counterparts.[13]

III. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This study utilizes in-depth interviews to extract valuable insights within the context of cultural differences from selected respondents. The interview process involves engaging participants through open-ended questions and discussions, allowing for a nuanced exploration of their perspectives, experiences, and opinions related to the research subject. The interviews are conducted to two Japanese Expatriates (Expatriate A & B) and five Indonesian Employee (Local A-E) who frequently interact with each other

in work-related contexts. This interview conducted using a semi-structured approach to ensure that the data collected remains focused and does not deviate from the context and producing targeted and relevant findings.

Based on interview, the researcher observed significant differences in communication styles between Japanese expatriates and Indonesian employees. Japanese expatriates tend to communicate in a structured and detailed manner, whereas Indonesians are sometimes less structured. This was expressed by Expatriate A in his statement, “*Sometimes Indonesians confuse me, what they say is unclear and lacks detail.*” This difference is also reflected in the responses from Indonesian employees, who mentioned needing greater effort to prepare data and anticipate follow-up questions from Japanese expatriates during discussions.

Secondly, communication from Japanese expatriates in the company is typically limited to work-related matters. Personal interactions usually only take place during specific occasions such as casual office events. In contrast, Indonesian employees place a high value on interpersonal relationships and engagement with colleagues. This was emphasized by Local B, who consistently tries to build light and casual communication with his team members and customers to maintain good cooperation. A similar approach is also taken by Mr. Local D, who always makes time to communicate with customers to foster positive relationships. This tendency is reinforced by the personalities of Local A and Local B, who fall into the multiactive category—cultures in which people prioritize relationships.

From the perspective of work ethics, the researcher identified three significant differences. The first concerns the perspective of Japanese expatriates and Indonesian employees towards work. Japanese expatriates place work as the most important thing in life, whereas for Indonesian employees, work is the second or third priority after religion and family. As a result, Japanese expatriates tend to be highly serious and committed to their jobs.

The second difference lies in the perception of time. Japanese expatriates consider time to be highly valuable. They use their free time to stay productive and engage in personal improvement. On the other hand, Indonesian employees believe that work should be done during working hours, and that free time should be used for leisure or for building good relationships with fellow employees or external stakeholders.

The final difference concerns future orientation. Japanese expatriates believe that the future must be prepared for starting now. They feel the need to work hard and be responsible in their roles. Although the ultimate goal may be similar, Indonesian employees tend to believe that there is no need to worry about an uncertain future. It is better to live and work well in the present, with the hope that doing so will lead to good outcomes in the future.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

After conducting an in-depth analysis and a comparative analysis of the differences in work ethics and communication styles among the interviewees, the author can propose solutions to address these differing perceptions as follow:

A. *Create Personal or Forum Discussion.*

This activity will facilitate structured discussion where both Japanese and Indonesian employees can openly share and reflect on their work values. The purpose of this activity is to build mutual understanding, reduce judgment or misinterpretation, and highlight common goals, such as team success or quality work. This activity will encourage the Japanese expatriates, who fall under the reactive category, to speak more frequently and express their ideas clearly so that they can be better understood by their subordinates. This activity can also foster engagement between Japanese expatriates and local employees, as most local employees place great importance on interpersonal relationships.

B. *Promote Work & Personal Life Balance*

Encourage work – personal life balance by respecting local norms, such as time for religious practices or family, without reducing the sense of responsibility in completing work. The purpose of this initiative is to prevent disengagement among Indonesian employees.

C. *Personal Development*

Offer voluntary upskilling opportunities, such as online training or language courses, during or outside working hours, with incentives or without obligations. The purpose of this activity is to engage both Japanese and Indonesian employees in self-improvement and to motivate Indonesian employees without imposing rigid expectations on their leisure time. Additionally, specialized training—such as intercultural communication or language courses—can help minimize potential areas of conflict in communication.

D. Leadership Training in Cultural Intelligence

Train both Japanese and Local Managers or Leaders in cultural intelligence (CQ) to better understand, adapt to, and lead across these differing work values. The purpose of this training is to recognizing the leaders that different expressions of responsibility and commitment can still yield high performance.

E. Building Effective Communication

By establishing clear and effective communication, all employees, both Japanese expatriates and local staff, will feel more comfortable expressing their opinions. Mutual understanding of each culture's characteristics is the key to successful communication. Japanese expatriates, who generally fall under the reactive culture category, require two-way communication and consensus-building in conversations. Additionally, they place high value on "chinmoku" or silent communication, where silence plays a very important role in maintaining harmony and avoiding direct conflict. Many people in Japan believe it is better to remain silent than to cause misunderstandings or trouble. This preference for silence is also tied to a strong awareness of social hierarchy within groups and society at large[14]. On the other hand, Indonesians, who are generally considered part of a multiactive culture, place great importance on interpersonal relationships with both coworkers and external stakeholders. As such, they require frequent compromise and tolerance in communication. However, while these are general cultural tendencies of Japan and Indonesia, a personalized approach is also necessary to achieve truly effective communication. The suggested personalized communication approaches are presented in the table below:

Table I. Communication Style Comparison and Personal Approach

Description	Hofstede's Theory	Hall's Theory	Lewis's Theory	Effective Communication to Talk With:
Expatriate A	Power Distance: High Uncertainty Avoidance: High	Low Context	Reactive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use a structured and hierarchical communication system 2. Use words that are clear, detailed, and easy to understand 3. Use direct communication 4. Avoid confrontation and use a diplomatic approach 5. Give time to provide responses and reflection
Expatriate B	Power Distance: High Uncertainty Avoidance: High	High Context	Reactive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use a structured, hierarchical, and easy-to-understand communication system 2. Use body language and tone of voice to support communication 3. Use indirect communication 4. Avoid confrontation and use a diplomatic approach 5. Give time to provide responses and reflection
Local A	Power Distance: Low Uncertainty Avoidance: High	Low Context	Multiactive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use egalitarian or equal communication 2. Use direct and open communication 3. Use words that are clear, detailed, and easy to understand 4. Use flexible and interactive communication
Local B	Power Distance: Moderate to High Uncertainty Avoidance: High	High Context	Multiactive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use a structured, hierarchical, and easy-to-understand communication system 2. Use body language and tone of voice to support communication 3. Use flexible and interactive communication

	Avoidance: High			
Local C	Power Distance: Low Uncertainty Avoidance: High	Low Context	Multiactive	1. Use egalitarian or equal communication 2. Use direct and open communication 3. Use words that are clear, detailed, and easy to understand 4. Use flexible and interactive communication
Description	Hofstede's Theory	Hall's Theory	Lewis's Theory	Effective Communication to Talk With:
Local D	Power Distance: High Uncertainty Avoidance: High	Low Context	Linear Active	1. Use a structured and hierarchical communication system 2. Use words that are clear, detailed, and easy to understand 3. Use direct and to-the-point communication 4. Use a logical and factual approach
Local E	Power Distance: High Uncertainty Avoidance: Moderate to High	High Context	Reactive	1. Use a structured, hierarchical, and easy-to-understand communication system 2. Use body language and tone of voice to support communication 3. Use indirect communication 4. Avoid confrontation and use a diplomatic approach 5. Give time to provide responses and reflection

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